

NOVEL STIFF AEROGEL-AEROGEL COMPOSITES FOR THERMAL INSULATION APPLICATION

Jessica Laskowski¹, Barbara Milow¹ and Lorenz Ratke¹

¹Institute of Materials Research, German Aerospace Center (DLR)
Linder Höhe, D-51147 Köln, Germany

Email: jessica.laskowski@dlr.de, web page: <http://www.dlr.de>

Keywords: Aerogel-aerogel composites, Thermal insulation, Cellulose aerogel, Silica aerogel, Resorcinol-formaldehyde aerogel

ABSTRACT

Aerogels are suitable materials for ultralight thermal insulation due to their properties of very low thermal conductivity <0.02 W/mK and low density <0.1 g/cm³ as a result of a high porosity (up to 99%) and their nanostructure. However, they are usually fragile and tend to release dust. We investigated aerogel-aerogel composites to develop new materials with optimal properties adapted to the application. In our study we embedded two different kinds of highly insulating granular aerogels in cellulosic aerogel: hydrophilic silica aerogel (SiO₂) and resorcinol-formaldehyde (RF) aerogel which were prepared by ourselves. In the first step a salt hydrate melt of 59 wt.-% Ca(SCN)₂ with 2 wt.-% of cellulose from cotton linters is prepared at 110 °C. Between 0.8-3.8 wt.-% of granular aerogel resulting in ≤ 36 vol.-% of granular material in the aerogel-aerogel composite is directly mixed into the melt. The hot melt is filled into a vessel after the cellulose is completely dissolved. A wet cellulose gel forms while cooling and builds a nanofibrillar felt structure. The composite gels are aged and washed in ethanol and are dried supercritically with CO₂. We obtained non-fragile materials with density about 0.06-0.17 g/cm³ and thermal conductivity about 0.036-0.044 W/mK. Compared to pure aerogels, embedding granular aerogel material into the structure of a cellulosic aerogel has a strong stiffening effect regarding the Young's modulus.

1 INTRODUCTION

An efficient thermal insulation is essential in order to reduce costs and to reduce the emission of CO₂. This global issue concerns many application fields, like aerospace (airplanes, spacecraft), ground-based vehicles, building constructions, air-conditioning systems or industrial processes. Aerogels have great potential to be used as thermal insulation material due to their properties of very low density (0.01-0.3 g/cm³) and low thermal conductivity (<0.02 W/mK) caused by their structure [1,2,3]. A high porosity (up to 99%), small pores of a few nanometers and the low density effects a limitation of thermal conductivity via the gas and the solid phase [4,5]. If the pores are smaller than the mean free path of a molecule in air (68 nm) thermal conductivity lower than that of free air (0.026 W/mK) can be reached. Compared to commonly used thermal insulation materials, like polymer foams polyurethane (0.020-0.029 W/mK) or expanded polystyrene (0.029-0.055 W/mK), inorganic wool (0.031-0.045 W/mK) or foam glass (0.038-0.050 W/mK) [6], aerogels seems to be much more effective.

Aerogels can be inorganic, organic or hybrids and are usually synthesized via a sol-gel reaction and suitable drying of the gel [7]. Approved processes in which a damage of the three-dimensional network of the gel during drying is avoided are the supercritical (mostly with CO₂) or freeze drying [8,9]. The first aerogel reported was the inorganic silica aerogel developed in 1931 by Kistler et al. [10,11]. He prepared silica aerogels via the sol-gel reaction of aqueous sodium silicate solution (waterglass) and hydrochloric acid and dried the gels obtained under supercritical conditions. Meanwhile, other routes are known for the preparation of silica aerogels, like the polymerization of alkoxy silanes (SiOR)₄ (e.g. tetramethylorthosilicate, TMOS) in a mixture of an organic solvent with water through hydrolysis and a condensation reaction [12].

The development of organic aerogels started later in the 1980s with resorcinol-formaldehyde (RF)

aerogels published by Pekala [13]. RF aerogels are synthesized via the sol-gel reaction of resorcinol (1,3-dihydroxybenzene) and formaldehyde in an aqueous solution and supercritical drying. The lowest value of thermal conductivity reported is 0.012 W/mK for a supercritically dried RF aerogel [14].

Using aerogels as insulation material is a challenge because they are mostly fragile and tend to release dust on handling. Therefore using a granular material instead of monolithic ones is more practicable. The granular aerogel can be fixed in a stable matrix to obtain a stable insulating product. The matrix of particulate composite can be polymers like polyurethane [15], melamine foam [16] or other aerogels [17,18]. Using an aerogel matrix is the best way to maintain the important characteristic properties of aerogels.

A potential matrix for particulate aerogel-aerogel composites is cellulosic aerogel since it consists of the re-growing and non-hazardous bio-polymer cellulose. Although the material is accepted as an aerogel the synthesis of cellulosic aerogels is not a classical sol-gel reaction as it is for inorganic aerogels. The synthesis is a combination of dissolution and regeneration of cellulose followed by drying resulting in a non-dusty and open porous material. The formation of a gel by using a suitable solvent agent is an important step in the synthesis. Known solvent agents are for example calcium thiocyanate ($\text{Ca}(\text{SCN})_2$) hydrate melt (59 wt.%) [19,20], NaOH/water [21] or NMMO/water [21,22]. In all cases the bio-polymer in solution builds a nanofibrillar felt structure while regeneration. The resulting aerogels usually have densities between 0.04-0.3 g/cm³ and lowest values for thermal conductivity published were 0.029-0.032 W/mK [23].

In our study we developed aerogel-aerogel composites consisting of cellulosic aerogel as the matrix embedding highly insulating granular aerogel. Granular silica aerogel and granular RF aerogel were tested and the interaction with the cellulosic matrix is investigated. The usage of cellulosic aerogels as a matrix material for insulation applications is evaluated as well. Characterization was performed under the aspect of structural (density, SEM), mechanical (compression test) and thermal properties (thermal conductivity).

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Chemicals used for the synthesis of cellulosic aerogels are cellulose powder (cellulose fibers, medium, Sigma Aldrich) obtained from cotton linters with the degree of polymerization (DP) of 201 and calcium thiocyanate $\text{Ca}(\text{SCN})_2 \cdot 4 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (95%, Sigma Aldrich). Hydrophobic granular silica aerogel (Lumira[®] aerogel particles) is supplied by Cabot Corporation (Germany) and granular RF aerogel is synthesized by us using the chemicals resorcinol (>98%, Sigma Aldrich), sodium carbonate Na_2CO_3 (puriss. p.a. $\geq 99.8\%$, Sigma Aldrich) and a 24% formaldehyde solution (not buffered, VWR BDH Prolabo). The washing step of the gels is performed with acetone (pure, technical grade, Th. Geyer) or ethanol (96%, denatured, Th. Geyer).

2.2 Synthesis

Preparation of granular silica aerogel

Hydrophobic granular silica aerogel were separated by sieving with mesh sizes of 0.25, 0.5 and 1 mm. They were then thermally treated at 600 °C for 3 days in order to get hydrophilic grains necessary for the preparation of aerogel-aerogel composites. Hydrophobic organic groups (methyl groups) decompose during the thermal treatment and hydrophilic grains are obtained.

Preparation of granular resorcinol-formaldehyde aerogel

In the first step monolithic resorcinol-formaldehyde (RF) aerogels were synthesized. Two different recipes similar to the recipe of Pekala [13] were applied both contains the molar ratios of resorcinol to formaldehyde (R/F) of 0.5 and of resorcinol to the catalyst (R/C) of 100. The molar ratio of resorcinol to water (R/W) is 0.003 (RF I) or 0.005 (RF II).

A solution of 13.76 g resorcinol in 727.08 g (RF I) or in 426.75 g (RF II) deionized water with 0.1325 g of the catalyst sodium carbonate is prepared in a beaker. When the solids are completely dissolved, 31.25 g of a 24% formaldehyde solution is added while stirring starting the sol-gel reaction of resorcinol with formaldehyde. After 30 minutes of stirring the solution is divided into parts of 100 mL each filled in a polypropylene vessel and stored 7 days in an oven at 85 °C. The gels are then removed from the vessel and washed in an acetone bath. A daily replacement of acetone by fresh one performed 8 days assures that water in the pores of the gel is completely removed and replaced by the solvent acetone. Finally, samples are dried with supercritical CO₂ (50 °C, 80 bar) in an autoclave and the aerogels are crushed and sieved with mesh sizes of 0.25, 0.5 and 1 mm.

Synthesis of aerogel-aerogel composites

Composites are synthesized similar to the synthesis of pure cellulosic aerogels [20] but with an additional step. 1.137 g of cellulose and 49.0 g of Ca(SCN)₂·4 H₂O are filled into a beaker and mixed with a stirring rod. Then, 7.8 mL of deionized water is added to obtain a suspension with 59 wt.% of Ca(SCN)₂ and 2 wt.% of cellulose. While frequently stirring the suspension is heated up to 110 °C with an oil bath and when the salt is melted 5, 10, 15 or 20 mL of granular aerogel is dispersed still stirring with the rod. The amount of granular aerogel is between 0.8-3.8 wt.% related to the complete approach. Cellulose is assumed to be completely dissolved when a clear solution in which no cellulose powder can be seen is obtained and the viscosity of the melt increases having then the consistency of honey. The hot melt is filled into a polypropylene sample box and the surface is covered by ethanol. The regeneration of cellulose starts while cooling below 80 °C in which cellulose builds a nanofibrillar felt structure. 24 h later, the gels are released from boxes and to remove the salt from pore space they are washed with ethanol by using a Soxhlet extractor. The washing step is finished when the test with Fe³⁺ ions proves qualitatively the absence of SCN⁻ ions. The presence of SCN⁻ ions leads to dark red solution caused by the red complex [Fe(SCN)₃(H₂O)₃]. A colorless solution shows therefore that the washing was sufficient. Finally, the gels are dried with supercritical CO₂ (55 °C, 90 bar) performed in autoclave.

2.3 Methods

Bulk density was determined using the envelope density analyzer GeoPyc® 1360 from Micromeritics. Specific surface area was obtained from nitrogen adsorption measurement with the analyzer TriStar® II from Micromeritics by using the BET method [24]. A field emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM) Merlin® from Zeiss was used to investigate the structure and the interfaces of the grains and the matrix after sputtering the sample with gold. The thermal conductivity was measured with the thermal constants analyzer type TPS 2500 from HotDisk AB. A compression machine from Latzke (Germany) was used to realize a uniaxial compression test on cubic samples (edge length about 15 mm) implemented with a pressure gauge with a maximum of 500 N. Young's moduli were calculated from slopes of stress-strain curves.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Structural properties

Aerogel-aerogel composites consisting of granular silica or resorcinol-formaldehyde (RF) aerogel embedded in a cellulosic matrix are of cylindrical shape with diameter about 43 cm and 1.7 cm height. The addition of silica aerogel in the cellulosic aerogel leads to a white material (Fig. 1, left) similar to pure cellulosic aerogel. RF-aerogel grains in the cellulosic matrix are visible dark brown in a white matrix (Fig. 1, right). Both materials seem to be more stable regarding compression in contrast to pure cellulosic aerogel, which are easily deformable with fingers. Additionally, the composites do not break on handling like grinding or cutting with a fine saw.

Figure 1: Photographs of aerogel-aerogel composites; left: cellulose aerogel/silica aerogel composite; right: cellulose aerogel/RF aerogel composite.

Densities of composites ρ as the function of volume fraction of aerogel grains ϕ_{grains} are shown in Fig. 2 (left) and are compared to pure components. Pure cellulosic aerogel ($\phi_{grains} = 0$) has very low density (0.04 g/cm^3). The addition of silica or RF aerogel causes an increase in density, since the density of silica is 0.15 g/cm^3 , of RF I is 0.13 g/cm^3 and of RF II is 0.16 g/cm^3 ($\phi_{grains} = 1$). Theoretically, density of two phase composites follows the relation

$$\rho = \phi_1\rho_1 + \phi_2\rho_2 + \Delta\rho \quad (1)$$

with densities of components ρ_1 and ρ_2 , volume fraction of components ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 and $\Delta\rho$ as a possible deviation from reaction of components in the synthesis. As demonstrated in the graph, there is no linear relation that would occur if $\Delta\rho$ is 0. All composites have higher density indicating a positive $\Delta\rho$. The main reason for the huge deviation is the shrinkage while washing and drying of the gels. A corrected density $\rho_{corr.}$, i.e. the theoretical density without shrinkage, can be calculated by applying Eq. 2:

$$\rho_{corr.} = \rho(1 - S_{rel}) \quad (2)$$

with density ρ measured and S_{rel} as the relative shrinkage measured after drying. Values of $\rho_{corr.}$ are presented in Fig. 2 (right). Densities of materials without shrinkage are much smaller than before but a linear relation in the whole range of volume fraction grains ϕ_{grains} is still not reached. A deviation is high in case of cellulose/RF composites and low in case of cellulose/silica composites. The observation of a positive $\Delta\rho$ points a change of density of components in the composites. In the synthesis granular aerogel is dispersed in the cellulose solution where water infiltrates the pores of the aerogel grains. This has two consequences: firstly, the molar ratio of water and $\text{Ca}(\text{SCN})_2$ was intended to be 6:1 but changes to a smaller water content due to the infiltration and this change might lead to a cellulosic aerogel with different properties (higher density). Secondly, the infiltration and the latter (second) drying of the granular material can cause swelling and shrinkage. Shrinkage would mean higher density of the embedded material and consequently composites with higher density are obtained.

The structure of composite aerogels was investigated by SEM (Fig. 3). Pure cellulosic aerogels (Fig. 3a) consists of a nanofibrillar three-dimensional structure with large pores reaching micrometer scale. This is a typical structure for polysaccharide aerogels synthesized via dissolution and regeneration of the bio-polymer and this structure can also be found in the composites (Fig. 3b, c). Pure silica aerogel (Fig. 3b) and pure RF aerogel (Fig. 3c) distinguish from cellulose because the structure is composed of three-dimensional connected nanoparticles with pores in the same dimension about a few nanometers. A higher magnification is necessary to illustrate clearly the structure. More important is the interface of the matrix with the grains which shows partly a direct contact (encircled). It seems that single cellulose fibrils are somehow connected with the grains. Interpenetration possibly occurs during synthesis when cellulose starts to regenerate. The process does not depend on the chemical composition of aerogel grains since it was observed with both species silica and RF. The porosity is the essential point enabling interpenetration of cellulose into the grains. When there is no direct contact of the matrix with the grains usually a huge gap larger than the pores in the cellulosic bulk material exists (e.g. Fig. 3c). In the gel, i.e. before drying, a direct contact of the components

surfaces might have existed but a huge gap arises from shrinkage. Contact between the components remains in spite of shrinkage where interpenetration is present.

Figure 2: Density ρ of aerogel-aerogel composites as the function of volume fraction of granular aerogel ϕ_{grains} RF I, RF II or silica; left: density measured; right: density corrected according to Eq.2 in case no shrinkage would happen during drying.

Figure 3: SEM images of a cellulosic aerogel (a) and of the interface of the cellulosic matrix and the granular silica aerogel (b) or the granular RF aerogel (c) in an aerogel-aerogel composite. Interpenetration occurs in the aerogel-aerogel composites (encircled).

Highly porous materials usually have high specific surface areas. The weight-based specific surface area S_m is obtained from BET method [24] and the volume-based surface area S_v can be calculated by multiplication with bulk density ρ :

$$S_v = \rho S_m \quad (3)$$

Theoretically, the volume-based surface area S_v of a two phase composite material should follow the linear relation

$$S_v = \phi_1 S_{v,1} + \phi_2 S_{v,2} \quad (4)$$

with $S_{v,1}$ and $S_{v,2}$ as the surface areas of the components and ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 as the volume fractions of the components. For our composites this means that S_v of composites should be between $11 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ (cellulosic aerogel) and $120 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ (silica aerogel), $85 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ (RF I) or $106 \cdot 10^6 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^3$ (RF II). As shown in the graph in Fig. 4 the linear relation does not exist for composites with RF aerogels in the whole range of ϕ_{grains} and S_v is much larger than the average. The deviation indicates a possible change of properties of the pure components in the composite what is in agreement with other observations made (density, SEM). Applying Eq. 4 seems to be too simple since effects changing properties like interpenetration or shrinkage of grains is not considered in the equation. In case of silica containing composites a linear relation is also not achieved in the whole range of ϕ_{grains} and the values are lower than the average. The different behaviours of granular silica and RF aerogels are not yet understood and more tests are necessary.

Figure 4: Volume based surface area S_v of aerogel-aerogel composites as the function of volume fraction of granular aerogel ϕ_{grains} RF or silica.

3.2 Thermal conductivity

Thermal conductivities λ of our materials were measured and the results as a function of volume fraction of granular aerogel ϕ_{grains} are shown in Fig. 5. The cellulosic aerogel is quite highly conductive ($\lambda=0.044 \text{ W/mK}$) because this kind of aerogel consists of a continuously connected fibrillar three-dimensional network as shown in chapter 3.1 and is therefore able to transfer heat unresisted through the solid backbone. Additionally, large pores enable heat conduction via the gas phase. We expected a decrease in thermal conductivity when embedding highly insulating granular aerogels into the structure. According to the Hashin-Shtrikman bounds [25,26] the resulting values of a two phase isotropic particulate composite should be even lower than the average of the pure components. RF (as a monolith) has about 0.023 W/mK and silica aerogel is declared to have just 0.012 W/mK before thermal treatment. Aerogel-aerogel composites with RF aerogel show a decrease in thermal conductivity compared to pure cellulose but the values of composites are mostly higher than the average. In contrast, the decrease with granular silica aerogel is marginal although the value of silica was expected to be lower. This observation indicates a significant structural change of the aerogel grains in the synthesis of composites especially for the silica aerogel. Silica aerogel might have lost the highly insulating property during thermal treatment what was performed to obtain hydrophilic grains. Furthermore, thermal conductivity might be larger in the composite because of possible densification of silica and RF grains due to shrinkage after the water contact in the cellulose solution and the “second” drying. Thermal conductivity depends on density as demonstrated in various publications [27,28] and therefore higher values can arise if density of a component increase. From SEM investigation we also found large gaps in the cellulosic matrix around the silica and the RF grains which are larger than pores in the bulk cellulose material. This would also enhance the thermal transport via the gas phase and sets a limitation in thermal insulation.

Figure 5: Thermal conductivity λ of aerogel-aerogel composites as the function of volume fraction of granular aerogel ϕ_{grains} RF or silica.

3.3 Mechanical properties

The stress-strain curve from uniaxial compression test of pure cellulosic aerogel exhibits a classical deformation curve for a porous material (Fig. 6, left). After the onset of irreversible deformation further deformation occurs at almost constant stress. A slight increase of compressive stress arises due to densification without causing cracks. In the test of pure monolithic RF aerogels small cracks in the bulk material occur noticeable by small spikes in the stress-strain curve. RF aerogels can stand higher stresses compared to pure cellulose as a result of higher density. A small difference between the two RF aerogels is observed after 10% strain because they also differ in density. RF II ($\rho = 0.16 \text{ g/cm}^3$) is more stable concerning densification than RF I ($\rho = 0.13 \text{ g/cm}^3$). Since the silica aerogel used was a granular material from the beginning, a compression test could not be performed.

Composite aerogels were tested and stress-strain curves of composites with 20-21 vol.% of granular aerogel with 0.5-1 mm grain size are shown in Fig. 6 (right). Much higher stresses are reached with composites with 21 vol.% of granular RF aerogel compared to both components RF and cellulose and no crack occurs. The mechanical property of pure RF aerogel defines the mechanical strength, therefore composites with RF II reaches higher stress than with RF I. The curve of the composite with 20 vol.% of silica aerogels proceeds similar to cellulose below 20% strain. Thus, no strengthening effect according to pure cellulose was achieved. After 20% strain densification starts in the composite and the curve now proceeds similar to cellulose/RF composites containing a strong increase.

Young's Moduli E are calculated from slope in the linear elastic region of stress-strain curves and are demonstrated in Fig. 7 as a function of bulk density ρ . Values obtained are between 1.5-4.2 MPa and partially increase with density. In general, E of cellulose/RF composites are larger than of cellulose/silica composites. As reported in literature [29,30], E correlates to a power of the bulk density for any kind of aerogel (silica aerogel, organic resorcinol-formaldehyde aerogel, carbon aerogel) and the power ranges from 3-4. This correlation explains the difference between the composites because densities of composites with RF are higher than with silica aerogel (see 3.1). However, a relation does not fit for all E obtained because some values are much lower than expected (e.g. samples about 0.16 g/cm^3 density). Inhomogeneity in the composite might influence the results. Young's moduli of pure materials cellulosic and RF are very low between 1.5-1.8 MPa (Table 1). Since composites have maximum $E=4.2 \text{ MPa}$ an improvement in stiffness was achieved by applying aerogel-aerogel composite technology.

Figure 6: Compressive stress-strain curves from uniaxial compression test; left: curves of pure RF aerogel and of cellulosic aerogel; right: curves of aerogel-aerogel composites with 20-21 vol.% of granular aerogel (0.5-1 mm grain size) compared to pure cellulosic aerogel. Composites do not break or become cracks during measurement. Cracks are noticeable by small spikes in the curve like it is noticeable in the curves of pure RF aerogels (arrows).

Figure 7: Young's Modulus E of aerogel-aerogel composites as the function of bulk density ρ . E was calculated from slope in the linear elastic region of stress-strain curves.

Table 1: Young's Modulus E of pure aerogels.

Aerogel	Young's modulus	
cellulose	1.5	[MPa]
RF I	1.8	[MPa]
RF II	1.8	[MPa]

4 CONCLUSION

Aerogel-aerogel composites consisting of highly insulating granular aerogel and cellulosic aerogel as the matrix can be produced by adding aerogel grains during the synthesis of a cellulosic aerogel. Resorcinol-formaldehyde (RF) aerogel and silica aerogel were tried both with very low thermal conductivity ($\lambda_{RF} = 0.023$ W/mK, $\lambda_{silica} = 0.012$ W/mK). The dispersion of granular aerogels (≤ 36 vol.%) in the cellulose solution does not prohibit the gel formation of cellulose but interpenetration occurs partially between the aerogels. Density obtained for the composites is 0.06-0.17 g/cm³ in dependence on the type and the volume fraction of grains. Properties of composites like density and

- [11] S. S. Kistler, Coherent Expanded Aerogels, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry*, **36**, 1932, pp. 52-64 (doi: [10.1021/j150331a003](https://doi.org/10.1021/j150331a003)).
- [12] C.J. Brinker and G.W. Scherer, Sol-Gel Science - The Physics and Chemistry of Sol-Gel Processing, Academic Press, London, 1990, pp. 97-216.
- [13] R.W. Pekala, Organic Aerogels from the Polycondensation of Resorcinol with Formaldehyde, *Journal of Materials Science*, **24**, 1989, pp. 3221-3227 (doi: [10.1007/BF01139044](https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01139044)).
- [14] X. Lu, M.C. Arduini-Schuster, J. Kuhn, O. Nilsson, J. Fricke and R. W. Pekala, Thermal Conductivity of Monolithic Organic Aerogels, *Science*, **255**, 1991, pp. 971-972 (doi: [10.1126/science.255.5047.971](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.255.5047.971)).
- [15] K. J. Chang, Y. Z. Wang, K. C. Peng, H. S. Tsai, J. R. Chen, C. T. Huang, K. S. Ho and W. F. Lien, Preparation of Silica Aerogel/Polyurethane Composites for the Application of Thermal Insulation, *Journal of Polymer Research*, **21**, 2014, pp. 1-9 (doi: [10.1007/s10965-013-0338-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10965-013-0338-7)).
- [16] P.-A. Bonnardel, S. Chausson and E. Gerardin (2014) Insulating composite materials comprising an inorganic aerogel and a melamine foam, WO Pat. # 2014198931 A1.
- [17] B. Milow and L. Ratke (2012) Aerogel-aerogel composite material, WO Pat. # 2012062370 A1.
- [18] J. K. Lee (2007) Organic aerogels reinforced with inorganic filler, US Pat. # 20070259979 A1.
- [19] H. Jin, Y. Nishiyama, M. Wada and S. Kuga, Nanofibrillar Cellulose Aerogels, *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, **240**, 2004, pp. 63-67 (doi: [10.1016/j.colsurfa.2004.03.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2004.03.007)).
- [20] S. Hoepfner, L. Ratke and B. Milow, Synthesis and Characterisation of Nanofibrillar Cellulose Aerogels, *Cellulose*, **15**, 2008, pp. 121-129 (doi: [10.1007/s10570-007-9146-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-007-9146-8)).
- [21] R. Gavillon and T. Budtova, Aerocellulose: New Highly Porous Cellulose Prepared from Cellulose-NaOH Aqueous Solutions, *Biomacromolecules*, **9**, 2008, pp. 269-277 (doi: [10.1021/bm700972k](https://doi.org/10.1021/bm700972k)).
- [22] F. Liebner, A. Potthast, T. Rosenau, E. Haimer, and M. Wendland, Cellulose Aerogels: Highly Porous, Ultra-Lightweight Materials, *Holzforschung*, **62**, 2008, pp. 129-135 (doi: [10.1515/hf.2008.051](https://doi.org/10.1515/hf.2008.051)).
- [23] S.T. Nguyen, J. Feng, S.K. Ng, J.P.W. Wong, V.B.C. Tan and H.M. Duong, Advanced Thermal Insulation and Absorption Properties of Recycled Cellulose Aerogels, *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, **445**, 2014, pp. 128-134 (doi: [10.1016/j.colsurfa.2014.01.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2014.01.015)).
- [24] S. Brunauer, P.H. Emmett and E. Teller, Adsorption of Gases in Multimolecular Layers, *Journal of the American Chemical Society*, **60**, 1938, pp. 309-319 (doi: [10.1021/ja01269a023](https://doi.org/10.1021/ja01269a023)).
- [25] Z. Hashin and S. Shtrikman, A Variational Approach to the Theory of the Effective Magnetic Permeability of Multiphase Materials, *Journal of Applied Physics*, **33**, 1962, pp. 3125-3131 (doi: [10.1063/1.1728579](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1728579)).
- [26] Z. Hashin, Assessment of the Self Consistent Scheme Approximation: Conductivity of Particulate Composites, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **2**, 1968, pp. 284-300 (doi: [10.1177/002199836800200302](https://doi.org/10.1177/002199836800200302)).
- [27] X. Lu, P. Wang, M.C. Arduini-Schuster, J. Kuhn, D. Büttner, O. Nilsson, U. Heinemann and J. Fricke, Thermal Transport in Organic and Opacified Silica Monolithic Aerogels, *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids*, **145**, 1992, pp. 207-210 (doi: [10.1016/S0022-3093\(05\)80457-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3093(05)80457-0)).
- [28] L.W. Hrubesh and R.W. Pekala, Thermal Properties of Organic and Inorganic Aerogels, *Journal of Materials Research*, **9**, 1994, pp. 731-738 (doi: [10.1557/JMR.1994.0731](https://doi.org/10.1557/JMR.1994.0731)).
- [29] A. Emmerling and J. Fricke, Scaling Properties and Structure of Aerogels, *Journal of Sol-Gel Science and Technology*, **8**, 1997, pp. 781-788 (doi: [10.1023/A:1018381923413](https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1018381923413)).
- [30] H.S. Ma, A.P. Roberts, J.H. Prévost, R. Jullien and G.W. Scherer, Mechanical Structure-Property Relationship of Aerogels, *Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids*, **277**, 2000, pp. 127-141 (doi: [10.1016/S0022-3093\(00\)00288-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3093(00)00288-X)).